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4 Combining phylogeny and co-occurrence 5 to improve single species distribution 6 models

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26

27 **Abstract:**

28 **Aim** We present a novel quantitative framework that combines information on phylogeny
29 and the spatial distributions of related species to enhance single species distributional
30 models commonly used in ecology.

31

32 **Innovation** While species distribution models (SDMs) are becoming increasingly
33 sophisticated, they rarely take into consideration species shared evolutionary histories.
34 Species are not independent entities, and phylogenies may capture how species have
35 configured their spatial distributions as a response to their ecological similarities and
36 interactions in space and through evolutionary times. Our framework provides a flexible
37 approach to include phylogenies as a surrogate for missing trait data within SDMs, and
38 may be particularly valuable for disentangling current and historical drivers of species
39 distributions and modelling data-poor species when their close-relatives are better-
40 sampled.

41

42 **Main conclusions** We demonstrate how including phylogenetic information can
43 significantly improve the fit of species distribution models using both simulations and
44 empirical examples, by up to 30% for certain species. We show that the potential of
45 phylogenies to improve model fit directly relates to the phylogenetic structure of species
46 distributions and suggest that our framework has the potential to reconcile the apparent
47 conflict between the current and historical drivers of biodiversity patterns.

48

49 INTRODUCTION

50 Identifying the underlying factors shaping species geographic distributions is a major
51 focus in ecology and biogeography (Hutchinson 1959). The modelling of species
52 distributions is an important field of research in its own right (e.g. Pearson & Dawson
53 2003, Thuiller 2007, Franklin 2009, Peterson et al. 2011), and encompasses techniques
54 such as bioclimatic envelope models, ecological niche models, and habitat suitability
55 models or species distribution models (SDMs hereafter). SDMs use partial (i.e.
56 incompletely sampled) occurrence data to infer species niches or distributions, and have
57 become a central tool for ecology and biodiversity sciences. These SDM techniques are
58 key parts of many tasks, such as estimating species' ecological niches (e.g., Blonder et al.
59 2014), predicting future ranges under climate change (e.g., Thuiller et al. 2005, Araújo et
60 al. 2005, Huntley et al. 2008, Lawler et al. 2009, Early & Sax 2011), designing protected
61 areas networks (e.g., Williams et al. 2005, Wilson et al. 2005, Araújo et al. 2011),
62 predicting the spread of invasive species (e.g., Broennimann et al. 2007, Peterson et al.
63 2008, Villemant et al. 2011, Guo et al. 2012, Early & Sax 2014) and diseases (e.g.,
64 Peterson et al. 2006, 2007), and even finding new populations and species by the
65 identification of suitable habitats of under-sampled taxa (Feria and Peterson 2002,
66 Raxworthy et al. 2003, Bourg et al. 2005, Vieites et al. 2009).

67

68 Despite the utility of SDMs, they have been criticised on the basis of their implicit
69 assumptions (e.g., that species distributions are at equilibrium with climate and that
70 niches are constant across time and space; Pearson et al. 2006; Araújo and Rahbek 2006),
71 and their misapplications (e.g. Araújo and Peterson 2012). Perhaps most critically,
72 several examples in the literature have demonstrated a limited predictive power of SDMs
73 (see e.g., Fig. 1c) that is most evident in their inaccuracy to project species models from
74 one time period to another (Pearson et al. 2006, Araújo and Rahbek 2006). These

75 shortcomings have fuelled the development of increasingly sophisticated models that
76 account for biotic interactions, dispersal (e.g. Araújo & Luoto 2007, Kearney et al. 2010,
77 Boulangéat et al. 2012, García-Valdés et al. 2013, Pollock et al. 2014), and functional
78 traits (Pollock et al. 2012, Algar et al. 2013, D'Amen et al. 2015) in addition to
79 commonly used environmental features (e.g., Thuiller et al. 2005).

80

81 One promising avenue of SDM development has been the integration of species'
82 functional traits, both for the modelled species and those that characterise its surrounding
83 ecological environment (Thuiller et al. 2004, McGill et al. 2006, Ackerly & Cornwell
84 2007, Pollock et al. 2012). Species traits underlie the mechanistic basis for the abiotic,
85 biotic, and dispersal axes that determine species distributions (Soberon 2007). Traits can
86 describe species' responses to their physical environment (measured by physiological
87 tolerance traits), their degree of competition or facilitation with other species, and their
88 dispersal ability. However, despite the many efforts directed at assembling large
89 databases on life-history, morphology and physiology (e.g. Jones et al. 2009, Kattge et al.
90 2011, Wilman et al. 2014), comprehensive data on traits is still unavailable for many
91 species, particularly those that are rare or cryptic (Nakagawa & Freckleton 2008).
92 Further, available trait data are often most complete for easy-to-measure traits, which
93 might not necessarily match to the traits that are likely most important to defining species
94 distributions. In many cases the physiologically-driven climatic tolerances central to
95 understanding species' associations with climate can only be determined through costly
96 experiments and thus are not available for most species. Phylogenies provide one solution
97 as they can be invoked as a proxy for both measured (Mace et al. 2003, Whitmee & Orme
98 2013) and unobserved (latent) traits (Rohr 2010). Importantly, phylogenies may better
99 reflect the complex processes generated by multiple traits operating simultaneously, such

100 as ecological assembly, than an incomplete representation of the traits directly involved
101 in that process (e.g. Mouquet et al. 2012).

102

103 Previous work has shown that the distribution of a particular species can often be
104 informed by the distribution of other species within the same guild (McGill et al. 2006,
105 Bahn & McGill 2007, Ricklefs 2013). Positive associations might reflect co-varying
106 affinities to environmental conditions across species, whereas negative associations might
107 reflect divergent niche preferences. Negative and positive associations among species
108 distributions can also arise through evolutionary or biogeographic events (e.g. via
109 speciation and extinction), though most often these would manifest at larger spatial scales
110 (Pearson & Dawson 2003). At local scales, competitive or facilitative interactions could
111 promote spatial patterns of disaggregation or aggregation, respectively (Gotelli et al.
112 2010), although these are less likely to drive regional scale distributions (Pearson &
113 Dawson 2003; but see e.g. Araújo & Luoto 2007). Because closely related species are
114 more likely to share ecological preferences (e.g. Wiens et al. 2010; Losos 2011), the
115 resemblance among species geographic distributions in space should correlate with the
116 length of their shared evolutionary histories. The spatial distributions of related species
117 could even have the potential to generate predictions for target species for which we have
118 no geographical data but only information on their phylogenetic placement. Surprisingly,
119 phylogeny has been largely ignored in the SDM literature despite growing evidence that
120 climate niches can show strong phylogenetic conservatism (Olalla-Tárraga et al. 2011,
121 Khaliq et al. 2015).

122

123 The integration of spatial and phylogenetic data has informed our understanding of
124 diverse ecological patterns and processes such as community assembly (Webb et al.
125 2002), the associations between ecological and evolutionary mechanisms shaping

126 ecogeographical patterns (e.g. Diniz-Filho et al. 2009; Kuhn et al. 2009; Peres-Neto et al.
127 2012; Morales-Castilla et al. 2013), and the variation in the invasiveness of introduced
128 species (Shaefer et al. 2011; Wilgen & Richardson 2011). Separately, functional
129 dissimilarities have been used to help explain species geographic distributions (Algar et
130 al. 2013; Gallien et al. 2015), and recent work has explored the relative importance of
131 phylogenetic and functional trait information in models of species turnover and
132 community composition (Rosauer et al. 2014; Chalmandrier et al. 2015). However, we
133 still lack a general method for incorporating phylogeny into single species SDMs. We
134 present here a novel conceptual and quantitative framework that addresses this gap (Fig
135 1). We illustrate our approach using simulations, and show that it performs well when
136 species' responses are phylogenetically conserved, and does not bias inference when they
137 are not. We then validate our method using empirical data on Nearctic carnivores,
138 European mammals and trees, and South African Fabacea, and show substantial
139 improvement in the predictive power of SDMs in a majority of cases.

140

141 **Linking phylogenetic and spatial information**

142 Technical details are provided below, here we briefly describe our general framework and
143 identify two fundamental questions: (1) how can phylogenetic information be
144 incorporated in SDM models of single species? And (2) when is phylogeny informative
145 for species distributions? Our approach links current species distributions to evolutionary
146 processes, contrasting the contribution of phylogeny (i.e., variable importance in a
147 modelling framework) to that of climatic or additional functional explanatory factors.
148 Thus, our approach also helps disentangle current and historical drivers of species
149 distributions (see e.g. Currie 1991, Ricklefs 2004). By doing so, we assume that traits
150 which are informative regarding species distributions are phylogenetic structured. Note,
151 that our proposed framework will not be informative in the absence of phylogenetic

152 structure in species distributions; however, we test the performance of our method in such
153 cases and show that it is not biased.

154

155 We draw upon two established bodies of literature. First, conceptual and empirical work
156 integrating functional traits into SDMs (McGill et al. 2006, Algar et al. 2012, Pollock et
157 al. 2012), while acknowledging the practical difficulties associated with their inclusion
158 (*e.g.*, in trait selection). Second, methodological advances linking the spatial,
159 environmental, and functional dimensions of species distributions (Leibold et al. 2004,
160 Leibold et al. 2010, Peres-Neto et al. 2012, Peres-Neto & Kembel 2015). We suggest
161 that, if species' traits map well onto species' phylogeny, then phylogeny itself could be
162 used to inform species distribution models in the absence of the relevant trait information.
163 From these principles, we develop a quantitative approach that includes phylogenetic
164 relationships within SDM to make predictions for species and, using simulated
165 communities, test the performance of our approach under different evolutionary models.
166 Importantly, our framework incorporates a scaling parameter that reveals the
167 phylogenetic scale at which phylogenetic information is most relevant to species
168 distributions; this parameter can also be used to detect when phylogeny is not informative
169 of a species' distribution. We use simulations to verify that our approach detects and
170 distinguishes between cases where phylogeny is and is not informative (*i.e.* to show that
171 our framework does not pick on signal in species spatial distributions that are not
172 phylogenetically structured), thus we test for phylogenetic signal in species distributions
173 rather than assuming it *a priori*. We then provide an empirical illustration of our
174 framework by applying it to four disparate systems spanning mammals and plants in three
175 continents. Our approach is flexible, and we see no reason it cannot be imbedded within
176 any SDM approach. We suggest it may be particularly valuable in modelling data-poor

177 species whose close-relatives are better-sampled. We demonstrate that our method can
178 improve the accuracy of empirical predictions by as much as 30%.

179

180 **METHODS**

181 **Incorporating phylogeny into SDMs: the phylogenetic predictor**

182 In commonly used SDM algorithms, the distribution of a given focal species j is
183 expressed by a vector (\mathbf{Y}_j ; Fig. 1a) and modelled as a function of an environmental
184 predictor matrix \mathbf{E} (composed by $\mathbf{E}_1, \mathbf{E}_2, \dots, \mathbf{E}_n$ columns, each representing a single
185 predictor; Fig. 1b). Model accuracy is then estimated by contrasting predicted values (\hat{Y}_j)
186 against the observed presences and absences of the focal species (\mathbf{Y}_j). However, any
187 given focal species is not geographically isolated and displays spatial patterns of co-
188 occurrence (positive or negative) with other phylogenetically closely related species,
189 expressed here as an n -by- S community matrix $\mathbf{L}=[l_{ik}]$, containing the presence and
190 absence information across n sites by S species (Fig. 1c).

191

192 Our framework departs from common SDMs in that it adds an additional n -by-1
193 phylogenetic predictor $\mathbf{P}=[p_i]$ that summarizes the amount of phylogenetic structure
194 contained across sites (see Fig. 1c; see below for its calculation). Here, phylogenetic
195 information is characterised as the phylogenetic distance of the focal species j (i.e., the
196 species being modelled) to the other species in the community matrix, expressed by an
197 $(S-1)$ -by-1 column vector \mathbf{G} , containing the phylogenetic distances between the target and
198 the remaining species (Fig. 1c). Therefore, our framework allows flexibility in the
199 relationship between species evolutionary relationships and their patterns of co-
200 occurrence: species co-distributions could decrease (i.e., phylogenetic similar species
201 have similar distributions – environmental filtering) or increase (i.e., phylogenetic similar
202 species have distinct distributions – competition) with phylogenetic distance. \mathbf{G} is then

203 translated it into its distributional context \mathbf{P} which is included as an additional predictor
204 in SDMs (see Fig. 1e). \mathbf{P} is generated simply as:

$$205 \quad P = [p_i] = \frac{L_{ij} \cdot G^{-1}}{\sum L_i} \quad (1)$$

206 As such, \mathbf{P} is a vector containing the average phylogenetic distance between the focal
207 species j and the other S species in the metacommunity across sites; note that the inverse
208 of \mathbf{G} is used, giving lower weight to the distributions of distantly related species. It
209 follows that a site containing only closely related species to the focal species will have a
210 greater value than a site where only distantly related species are present. In this way, if
211 closely related species tend to share common sites, the expected model slope of the target
212 species on the phylogenetic predictor will be positive. Conversely, if more distant species
213 tend to co-exist with the target species the expected model slope will be negative. As
214 described above, \mathbf{P} is then simply included as an additional predictor in the SDMs (see
215 Fig. 1e). In our simulations, we used logistic regression for simplicity (see Appendix S1
216 in Supporting Information), but note that vector \mathbf{P} can be used as a phylogenetic predictor
217 within any SDM approach (e.g., GLMs, neural networks, classification trees). Below we
218 illustrate our approach using only a single vector \mathbf{P} , although multiple phylogenetic
219 predictors could be used to address differing processes shaping species' co-distributions.
220 However, we caution that such complex models could be difficult to interpret and that co-
221 estimating the phylogenetic scale of multiple predictors would present additional
222 challenges (see below).

223

224 Our proposed method to translating phylogenetic information into a spatial context
225 represents one out of many possible approaches. For example, it would be possible to
226 compute \mathbf{P} based on phylogenetic eigenvectors (Diniz-Filho et al. 1998), which have
227 been broadly used in the macroecological literature to disentangle evolutionary versus
228 ecological mechanisms shaping biogeographic gradients of, for example, body size

229 (Ramirez et al. 2008; Diniz-Filho et al. 2009), flowering times (Kuhn et al. 2009), and
230 range size (Morales-Castilla et al. 2013; Peres-Neto et al. 2012). We use phylogenetic
231 distances here to obviate the need for eigenvector selection and for greater transparency
232 in the interpretation of **P**. (i.e. higher values of **P** in a locality indicate a higher probability
233 of finding the target species at that locality). Another alternative would be to explore
234 Phylogenetic Generalised Linear Mixed Models (PGLMM; Ives & Helmus 2011), which
235 use random effects to account for phylogenetic co-variation, but the size of macro-
236 ecological datasets makes fitting such models challenging (if not impossible) using
237 current implementations (Kaldhusdal et al. 2015).

238

239 **Simulation assessment of the framework**

240 The premise for incorporating a phylogenetic predictor into SDMs is that the spatial
241 distribution of a species reflects its ecological requirements, which are inherited through
242 evolutionary time (i.e. there is a phylogenetic signature in the spatial distribution of
243 species). Our approach does not explicitly account for historical or contingent effects
244 (e.g. dispersal limitation, biotic interactions), however, the phylogenetic predictor can
245 implicitly capture such events if they result in phylogenetic patterning that is spatially
246 structured. To assess the performance of the proposed framework, we compared its
247 ability to correctly retrieve species distributions within simulated communities structured
248 according to different levels of phylogenetic conservatism. We simulated community
249 matrices structured on traits matching to one of three evolutionary processes (see
250 Appendix S2 for details on simulations). First, we considered a strongly conserved
251 phylogenetic process, where close relatives are extremely similar to one-another
252 (modelled with Pagel's [1999] $\delta = 0.01$). Second, a Brownian Motion (BM) process,
253 which is a common model of trait evolution representing a process where expected
254 differences across species trait values are proportional to the evolutionary time separating

255 them. And third, an evolutionarily labile process where most trait evolution among
256 species is very recent and thus there is very limited similarity among close relatives
257 (modelled with Pagel's [1999] $\delta = 10.0$). Simulated communities were then structured on
258 a trait generated under one of the three models, above and an environmental gradient
259 drawn from a normal distribution $\sim N(0,1)$. Full details of the simulations are provided in
260 Appendix S1. The resulting communities show markedly different spatial patterns of
261 phylogenetic aggregation in space (co-distribution of related species) depending on the
262 evolutionary model (see Fig. S1.1 in Supporting Information), from strong spatial
263 phylogenetic aggregation ($\delta = 0.01$) to phylogenetically random structure ($\delta = 10.0$). We
264 evaluated model performance using explained deviance (D^2 , Guisan & Zimmermann,
265 2000), which relates closely to other model fit metrics.

266

267 **The optimum phylogenetic scale**

268 The phylogenetic predictor **P** combines information on the phylogenetic distances among
269 species with the spatial co-occurrence of all species in the community matrix (see above).
270 While there is repeated evidence for interspecific competition driving spatial patterns of
271 segregation among close relatives (e.g. Goldberg et al. 1999, Kurle et al. 2008),
272 segregation patterns at larger phylogenetic scales could also arise, for example, via the
273 process of allopatric speciation (see Warren et al. 2014). However, it is not only close
274 relatives that may be informative; because different aspects of species niches may evolve
275 at different phylogenetic scales (Ackerly et al. 2006), phylogenetically distant species
276 may also help inform estimates of the focal species distribution.

277

278 To modulate the influence exerted by the distributions of closely *versus* distantly related
279 species, we included a weighting parameter α in the calculation of the phylogenetic
280 predictor **P**:

281
$$P_{\alpha} = [p_{\alpha_i}] = \frac{L_{ij} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-G_j}{\alpha}\right)}{\sum L_i} \quad (2)$$

282 where α modifies the relative phylogenetic distance that separates the focal species j from
283 the rest of species in the community matrix (\mathbf{G}). When $1 > \alpha > 0$, more distantly-related
284 species are down-weighted, while with values $\alpha > 1$ distantly related species are given
285 increasing weight (see Fig. 3a-e). For α values much greater than 1 ($\alpha \gg 1$), all values of
286 \mathbf{G} approach ~ 1.0 (Fig. 3d) such that phylogenetic distance is no longer informative, and
287 P_{α} would equal a vector of ones with a number of elements equal to the number of sites in
288 the metacommunity matrix (akin to the null or intercept model). The optimal α value is
289 estimated by an iterative procedure that maximizes the α value for which P_{α} best predicts
290 the distribution of any particular target species. This is analogous to a model selection
291 procedure, in which we choose α to maximize the deviance explained by a given model
292 and data, but alternative model selection techniques (e.g. based on AIC, BIC) could be
293 implemented easily.

294

295 We evaluated the effect of α on the predictive ability of the phylogenetic predictor P_{α}
296 through simulations. We first simulated the distributions of species within
297 metacommunities under strong trait phylogenetic conservatism (i.e. Pagel's $\delta = 0.01$) as
298 described above (see also Appendix S1 in Supporting Information). We then computed
299 phylogenetic predictors for three fixed values of alpha (i.e. $\alpha=0.5$, $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=5$). In
300 addition, for 100 randomly selected species, we computed 100 phylogenetic predictors at
301 varying levels of α (100 intervals within the range $50 > \alpha > 0$ see Appendix S1 in
302 Supporting Information) to more thoroughly explore the relationship between explained
303 deviance and α .

304

305 **Quantifying phylogenetic structure in species distributions**

306 Our framework assumes phylogenetic structure in species distributions. However,
307 empirical data on the existence of phylogenetic signal in the geographic distribution of
308 species is controversial, and numerous examples for both presence (e.g., Morales-Castilla
309 et al. 2013) and absence of signal (e.g., Ricklefs et al. 2011) are found in the literature. As
310 such, phylogenetic signal in species distributions should be tested rather than assumed *a*
311 *priori*. We propose here a straightforward method to evaluate phylogenetic structure in
312 species distributions that simply uses the first two axes of a Correspondence Analysis
313 (CA) to characterise the spatial structure of the community matrix **L**. CA is a multivariate
314 ordination technique designed for contingency tables and commonly used in ecology to
315 summarize spatial data in incidence matrices (ter Braak 1985). CA can be seen as a
316 technique to find latent site (e.g., environmental gradients) and species (e.g., traits) scores
317 that maximize their correlation (Williams 1952). We choose the first two CA axes
318 because they account for most of the variance in the spatial structure within **L**.
319 Phylogenetic signal can then be estimated for the CA column (species) scores using
320 standard metrics such as Pagel's (1999) λ or Blomberg et al.'s (2003) K . Both parameters
321 quantify phylogenetic non-independence in continuous traits relative to a BM model of
322 evolution, with values of 0 indicating no phylogenetic signal in the data and values of 1.0
323 consistent with a BM model.

324

325 **Case studies**

326 To illustrate the utility of phylogenetic predictors to inform the geographic distributions
327 of species empirically, we examined four diverse case studies for which we have reliable
328 regional occurrence data and well resolved phylogenetic trees: 29 Nearctic carnivore
329 species, 126 species of Western Palaearctic mammals, 75 species of Western Palaearctic
330 trees, and 116 species of Southern African Fabaceae plants (see Appendices S2 and S3 in
331 Supporting Information for detailed information about the datasets).

332

333 First, we assessed phylogenetic structure in the spatial structure of each community data
334 matrix, as described above (see Table 1).

335

336 Second, we computed each species' phylogenetic predictor P_α , optimizing the parameter
337 α as described above (see Appendix S1 in Supporting Information). Note again, that
338 SDMs were generated using logistic regression. We then compared the explanatory
339 power of computed phylogenetic predictors against that of random (non-phylogenetic)
340 predictors assuming a similar optimization procedure. This randomisation procedure
341 compares the fit of \mathbf{P} with other predictors that share all aspect of \mathbf{P} other than its
342 phylogenetic signal, allowing us to distinguish between the influence of phylogeny and
343 other latent factors such as environment.

344

345 Third, we explored the ability of the phylogenetic predictor to improve simple SDMs
346 using environmental variables. We contrasted environmental-SDMs informed by two
347 environmental predictors (mean annual temperature and annual precipitation) and
348 phylogenetic-SDMs informed by the same environmental predictors plus the
349 phylogenetic predictor. We then compared the variation in model fits using common
350 metrics of model accuracy (i.e., variation in true positives and in true negatives, variation
351 in error rates and variation in explained deviance) and the average importance of each
352 predictor using random forest models (by measuring model accuracy decreases as
353 predictor values are permuted within a random forest modelling context, Archer & Kimes
354 2008; see Appendix S2 in Supporting Information for more details). Finally, to
355 understand the variation in model fit across species, i.e. why some species models can be
356 greatly improved by the inclusion of the phylogenetic predictor P_α whilst others cannot,
357 we explored the relationships between deviance in species distributions explained by P_α

358 and three potential correlates: range size, explained deviance by environment alone, and
359 evolutionary distinctiveness (see Appendix S4 in Supporting Information).

360

361 **RESULTS**

362 **Simulations**

363 Our simulations showed that the phylogenetic predictor has predictive power to model
364 species distributions, but that this power, as expected, varies with the underlying model
365 of trait evolution used in simulating communities (see Fig. 2). When communities were
366 simulated assuming strong phylogenetic conservatism (Pagel's $\delta = 0.01$) and Brownian
367 models, phylogenetic predictors significantly out-performed random, non-phylogenetic,
368 predictors (see Fig. 2). When traits were evolved under a more labile evolutionary
369 process (Pagel's $\delta = 10$), phylogenetic predictors were no better than random (Fig. 2).
370 These results demonstrate that our method can correctly identify and make use of
371 phylogenetic signal when present, and that it does not spuriously detect pattern where
372 there is none (see Fig. 2 and Fig. S1.2 in Supporting Information). This is both re-
373 assuring and intuitive: when there is no phylogenetic signal in the spatial structure of
374 species it would be unreasonable to expect phylogeny to inform species distributions.
375 Further, we show that the phylogenetic predictors can explain similar model deviance to
376 the original trait used to structure species distributions, but again only when there is
377 phylogenetic structure in the data (see Fig. S1.3 in Supporting Information).

378

379 We show that deviance explained by phylogenetic predictors has a monotonic
380 relationship with α (See Fig. S1.3 in Supporting Information), which scales the relative
381 importance of close and distant relatives. Thus adjusting the weight given to the co-
382 distribution of relatives has the potential to build a more informative phylogenetic
383 predictor by selectively weighting the distribution of close of distant relatives. For $\alpha > 1$

384 (but not $\alpha \gg 1$), increasing level of the parameter generally increases the explanatory
385 power of the phylogenetic predictor, suggesting that phylogeny can inform across a
386 variety of phylogenetic scales (Fig. 4). For values of $\alpha \gg 1$, phylogeny becomes
387 uninformative (see Fig. 3). We suggest to optimize α by iteratively fitting the focal SDM
388 with phylogenetic predictors computed for differing α 's between zero and the maximum
389 phylogenetic distance in \mathbf{G} , and selecting the value of α that yields the best performing
390 phylogenetic predictor (e.g., based on SDM model accuracy metrics or error rates; see
391 Fig. S1.3 in Supporting Information).

392

393 **Case studies**

394 Although in all empirical examples the phylogenetic signal in spatial structure was less
395 than Brownian expectations (i.e. all $\lambda < 1.0$ and all $K < 1.0$), it was significantly different
396 from random (Table 1) and thus we expected phylogenetic predictors to be informative
397 for species distributions. In the case of Western Palaearctic mammals, phylogenetic
398 signal was only significant for Blomberg's K ($K=0.204$; $P \leq 0.008$). Based on our
399 simulation results (see Fig. 2), we would expect a weaker performance of the
400 phylogenetic predictors for this dataset.

401

402 The average explanatory power of the phylogenetic predictor varied across the empirical
403 datasets, from an average $D^2 = 0.196$ for Nearctic carnivores to an average $D^2 = 0.057$ for
404 South African Fabaceae species, but in the majority (65.5% of carnivores, 83.7% of
405 Fabaceae plants, and 59.5% and 66.7% of European mammals and trees, respectively) of
406 cases the phylogenetic predictor explained more deviance than random expectations (Fig.
407 5). Further, model accuracy of phylogenetic-SDMs generally outperformed that of
408 environmental-SDMs (Fig. 6a-e), although the distributions of a few species (belonging
409 to the W. Palaearctic mammals and S. African Fabaceae datasets) were better modelled

410 by environmental-SDMs alone (Fig. 6b-c,e). While the phylogenetic predictor was not
411 the most relevant predictor on average in any of the empirical dataset, it was always at
412 least as important as the second-most important environmental predictor (Fig. 6). Taken
413 together, these results indicate that our phylogenetic approach has the potential to
414 improve SDMs, adding as much explanatory power as commonly used environmental
415 variables.

416

417 While the contribution of phylogenetic predictors was mostly statistically significant
418 (environmental SDMs were improved for 96.5% of carnivores, 88.1% of mammals,
419 98.6% of trees and 84.5% of Fabacea plants; see Fig. 6), performance varied among
420 species. Range size and explained deviance by environment were unreliable predictors of
421 the explained deviance by P_{α} (see Fig. S3 and Appendix S3). However, explained
422 deviance by P_{α} consistently, albeit weakly, decreased with evolutionary distinctiveness
423 (Carnivora $r = -0.136$, Fabaceae $r = -0.080$, Mammals $r = -0.043$, Trees $r = -0.299$, and
424 birds $r = -0.128$; see Fig. S4 and Appendix S4). We would expect that the most
425 evolutionary distinct species would also be more ecologically distinct, and thus their
426 distribution would resemble less the distributions of other species in the community
427 matrix. It follows that our approach, which predicts species by drawing strength from
428 closely related species' distributions, would be less informative for such cases.

429

430 **DISCUSSION**

431 Our framework establishes a conceptual link between the geographical distribution of
432 species, their ecological requirements or constraints, and their evolutionary history. It is
433 clear that species are not independently distributed in space: they assemble together with
434 other species within communities on the basis of their shared ecological requirements and
435 biotic interactions. Our framework combines information on the co-distribution of species

436 and their phylogeny (as a proxy for ecological similarity, including missing information
437 on environmental affinities that are themselves phylogenetically structured), and is thus a
438 valuable tool for enhancing SDMs. Nevertheless, and similar to other approaches that
439 examine the structure of multiple communities (Ives & Helmus 2011), the composition of
440 the phylogenetic predictor will be contingent upon the set of species included within the
441 community data matrix. There is no clear answer as to how best to define the appropriate
442 limits of this matrix. However, our α weighting parameter provides a flexible model
443 fitting approach that allows variable weights across different phylogenetic distances,
444 clades and species. We evaluated our approach on diverse clades, differing in richness
445 (i.e. from 29 species of Nearctic carnivores to 116 species of South African Fabaceae
446 plants), phylogenetic depth (i.e. from the family to the class taxonomic level) and spatial
447 extent (i.e. from communities of 42Km² to communities of 96Km²). Despite this large
448 variation, we show that the inclusion of the phylogenetic predictor consistently improves
449 the fit of SDMs, although power tends to decrease as both spatial resolution and number
450 of species increases and as taxonomic resolution decreases (see Fig. 5).

451

452 The ability of the phylogenetic predictor to improve SDMs is predicated on the existence
453 phylogenetic structure in species distributions. However, as suggested by our empirical
454 case studies, such structuring may be common. For example, if closely related species
455 share ecological preferences in proportion to their shared evolutionary history then their
456 environmental niches should also co-vary, which could in turn have a detectable signal in
457 their spatial distributions. Additional processes such as historical biogeographic events
458 (e.g. past colonization events) or vicariant speciation etc. could also generate similar
459 spatial patterns of resemblance (Morales-Castilla et al. 2012). Our phylogenetic predictor
460 is agnostic as to the process underlying spatial patterns of covariance. In our framework,
461 the phylogenetic predictor can be considered simply as a latent trait used as a proxy for

462 ecological similarity among species. Analogous latent variable approaches have been
463 utilised to model species richness (Diniz-Filho & Bini 2005), community composition
464 (Jackson et al. 2001) and even single species distributions (McInerny & Purves 2011).
465 Such approaches have proven useful in accounting for predictor uncertainty or improving
466 predictive power (McInerny & Purves 2011); an advantage of our approach is in the
467 interpretability of the phylogenetic predictor. In addition, we suggest that our framework
468 allows us to move beyond the controversy over whether species distributions are driven
469 primarily by current climate or evolutionary history (Currie 1991, Ricklefs 2004,
470 Mittlebach et al. 2007) as it incorporates both into models and allows us to quantify their
471 relative importance.

472

473 In our results (as in most modelling exercises), species distributions are usually not fully
474 explained by the considered predictors. Unexplained variation can be in the form of either
475 missing site predictors (i.e., environmental variables) or species-specific characteristics,
476 which may reflect, for example, differences in dispersal abilities or the influence of biotic
477 interactions. One important question is therefore, which source (site or species) of
478 unexplained variation remains after fitting a given model. Analysing the structure of
479 predicted probabilities and classification errors across entire sets of species (i.e., a
480 metacommunity) can be helpful. In our example, classification errors show a somewhat
481 stronger site-wise structure for phylogenetic-only-SDMs and are structured more across
482 species for environmental-only-SDMs, as can be represented by the structuring of
483 classification errors in the metacommunity matrix (see Fig. S5 in Supporting
484 Information). Joint-SDMs, using both phylogenetic and environmental predictors, thus
485 sensibly reduce predictive errors from phylogenetic-only-SDMs (by 36.5% for false
486 negatives and 46.5% for false positives) and environmental-only-SDMs (by 18.5% for
487 false negatives and 22.1% for false positives) (see Fig. S5 in Supporting Information).

488 Importantly, by looking at the structure of classification errors we can, therefore, identify
489 the type of variables linked to ecological and evolutionary processes that are missing
490 from the model. This identification becomes then an important endeavour in itself, and
491 could allow for further model improvement by the inclusion of missing variables.
492

493 Our approach requires more data than traditional SDMs: a phylogeny and information on
494 the co-distribution of species closely related to the target species. However, current SDM
495 frameworks have been criticised because they perform poorly when predicting species
496 distributions across different spatial and temporal contexts (e.g. Araújo and Rahbek
497 2006), and our work adds to a growing body of approaches attempting to account for
498 species traits and biotic interactions (Boulangéat et al. 2012), and ecomorphological
499 landscapes (see Algar et al. 2013), all of which call for additional input data. Importantly,
500 we think the types of data required for our model fitting are quite common. Species co-
501 occurrences are frequently recorded in the ecological literature, and if phylogenetic data
502 are difficult to find, our method could be applied using distances among taxonomic levels
503 as a surrogate. Further, our **P** predictor is intended to reflect unmeasured elements of the
504 environment (along with other processes that are spatially and phylogenetically
505 structured). Thus **P** provides a way to compensate for limited environmental data: if
506 complete environmental (and historical) information were used, we would not expect **P** to
507 be a powerful predictor of species' distributions. As with any SDM approach, the choice
508 of environmental predictors (Araújo & Peterson 2012) and modelling approach (e.g.,
509 Jiménez-Valverde & Lobo 2007; Lobo et al. 2010; Barbet-Massin et al. 2012; Rocchini et
510 al. 2011) will affect the predictive power and biological insight that can be derived when
511 using our phylogenetic predictive approach.

512

513 Our method has a number of benefits with the potential to complement next-generation
514 SDMs. First, it creates phylogenetic predictors for all species and so can be used in
515 combination with functional (Pollock et al. 2012) or morphological (Algar et al. 2013)
516 trait data and with biotic interactions or dispersal metrics (Boulangéat et al. 2012).
517 Second, we suggest that species distribution hindcasts (Nogués-Bravo et al. 2010) and
518 forecasts (Thuiller et al. 2004), which project species distributions to past or future
519 environments, respectively, using SDMs generated using current climate, could be
520 improved because phylogenetic predictors may better capture the multiple processes
521 determining the spatial configuration of species. Third, species for which we have few
522 records could be predicted on the basis of their close relatives for which we have more
523 data. This could be particularly important for conservation prioritisation (Trindade-Filho
524 et al. 2012) because threatened (rarer) species often have less data. In addition, we also
525 suggest that there are many promising avenues of future research. For example, exploring
526 more explicit and varied models of trait evolution using transformations of the underlying
527 phylogenetic variance-covariance matrix and, the fitting of multiple phylogenetic
528 predictors simultaneously within a single model given that species distributions are likely
529 shaped by multiple processes (e.g. Estrada et al. 2016) and that traits may follow different
530 evolutionary models across the phylogeny (i.e., non-stationary trait evolution, Revell et
531 al. 2012).

532

533 **CONCLUSIONS**

534 Over the last two decades, the ecological literature has markedly benefitted from the
535 insights provided by the multiple applications of SDMs (Peterson et al. 2011) and
536 phylogenetics (e.g., Cavender-Bares et al. 2009, Vamosi et al. 2009, Mouquet et al.
537 2012). Notable examples include forecasting future species distributions (e.g., Araújo et
538 al. 2005), unravelling the process of community assembly (e.g., Graham et al. 2009),

539 predicting the structure of ecological networks (e.g., Rezende et al. 2007), and improving
540 our understanding of the relationships between ecosystem functioning and diversity (e.g.
541 Cadotte et al. 2009). Here we combine advances across these fields, and demonstrate,
542 using both simulations and empirical data, how phylogenetic information can improve
543 models of species' spatial distributions. We suggest that the inclusion of phylogenetic
544 predictors into SDMs is particularly powerful when species distributions are
545 phylogenetically structured, and species are nested within clades with many close
546 relatives. The use of phylogenetic predictors in SDMs has the potential to (1) provide a
547 better understanding of the relative contributions of ecological versus evolutionary
548 processes in shaping single species distributions, and (2) improve the accuracy of SDMs,
549 especially when applied to data deficient species or in making forecasts, for example,
550 during biological invasions or with climate projections.

551

552

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556

557 **Supporting Information**

558 Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of this article at the
559 publisher's web-site.

560 **Appendix S1.** Simulation analyses.

561 **Appendix S2.** Case studies, data extraction and distribution modelling.

562 **Appendix S3.** List of species included within each empirical dataset.

563 **Appendix S4.** Potential drivers of variation in phylogenetic predictor performance.

564 **Appendix S5.** Mapping predicted probabilities and classification errors.

565 **Appendix S6.** R scripts.

566

567

568 **Biosketch**

569 **Ignacio Morales-Castilla** is a postdoctoral researcher working in macroecology, biogeography
570 and macroevolution. He is interested in understanding the factors that determine species
571 distributions and interactions to better predict changes in ecosystem composition and functioning
572 derived from global change. He has recently developed conceptual and methodological
573 frameworks allowing to integrate phylogenetic, geographic and functional information to improve
574 predictions of both species distributions and species interactions.

575

576

577

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- 863

864 **Table 1.** Phylogenetic signal in the first axes of a correspondence analysis (CA) applied to the
865 community matrix of the five empirical examples. The first CA axes summarize most of the
866 variation in the spatial structure of a community data matrix. If the first CA axes are not
867 phylogenetically structured, then there is no reason to expect an evolutionary signature on species
868 distributions, and thus calculating phylogenetic structure in the CA axes can be used as a
869 preliminary test to determine the utility of including a phylogenetic predictor in a SDM.

Taxa	number of sites	number of species	CA axis	λ	p	K	p
Carnivora	1938	29	1	0.591	0.049	0.328	0.026
			2	0.282	0.093	0.280	0.139
Fabaceae	417	116	1	0.360	0.001	0.125	0.140
			2	0.000	1.000	0.053	0.839
W. Palearc. mammals	1832	136	1	0.114	0.266	0.204	0.008
			2	0.072	0.283	0.117	0.642
W. Palearc. trees	1810	47	1	0.670	0.001	0.134	0.004
			2	0.152	0.490	0.085	0.150

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874 **Figure legends**

875 **Figure 1.** Quantitative framework workflow. In a typical SDM, the geographic
876 distribution of a focal species, *Pipistrellus pipistrellus* in the example (A), is represented
877 by a vector \mathbf{Y}_j with ones (presences, in red) and zeros (absences, in yellow) that is
878 modelled against a set of environmental predictors (i.e. \mathbf{E}_1 , \mathbf{E}_2 and \mathbf{E}_3). The result is a
879 continuous distribution of probabilities \hat{Y}_j (B) that can be mapped and evaluated against
880 the observed distribution (C). Species \mathbf{Y}_j is spatially co-distributed with other species
881 present in the community matrix \mathbf{L} . The phylogenetic relationships between \mathbf{Y}_j and the
882 rest of species in \mathbf{L} , can be expressed by a vector of phylogenetic distances \mathbf{G} (D). A
883 phylogenetic predictor, \mathbf{P} , resulting from the combination of \mathbf{L} and \mathbf{G} , summarizes the
884 phylogenetic structure found at each site (D). Finally, \mathbf{P} can complement environmental
885 predictors in a SDM (E), and improve prediction accuracy (F) with respect to the
886 environment only SDM (C).

887

888 **Figure 2.** Model accuracy measured by explained deviance in the distribution of species
889 within community matrices simulated under three different evolutionary processes.
890 Community data matrices are simulated using a strongly phylogenetically structured trait
891 (A), a trait evolved according to a Brownian Motion (BM) model of evolution (B) and a
892 phylogenetically labile trait without any phylogenetic signal (C). Boxplots reflect
893 accuracy of models using either the phylogenetic predictor computed for each modelled
894 species (blue) or (non-phylogenetic) random predictors generated 100 times for each
895 modelled species (orange) (see Appendix S1 in Supporting Information for details on
896 Simulation analyses).

897

898 **Figure 3.** Effect of α on branch length, phylogenetic distance, and calculation of the
899 phylogenetic predictor, exemplified on a four-tipped phylogeny where species m

900 represents the focal species. A value of $\alpha = 1.0$ has no effect on vector \mathbf{G} representing
901 phylogenetic distances from the focal species m to the rest of species (i.e. n , o and p) (A).
902 Values of $\alpha < 1.0$ increase the distances in \mathbf{G} and have the effect of minimizing the
903 influence of distantly related species (i.e. o and p) when the exponential of $-\mathbf{G}$ is taken
904 (B). Values of $\alpha > 1.0$ have the opposite effect by decreasing distances in \mathbf{G} and
905 increasing the influence of distantly related species (i.e. o and p) when the exponential of
906 $-\mathbf{G}$ is taken (C). Finally, for values of $\alpha \gg 1.0$, the relevance of both closely and distantly
907 related species tends to one (D) and the relationship between phylogenetic distance and
908 the term $\exp(-\mathbf{G} / \alpha)$ becomes linear and constant (E). Note that labelled branch lengths
909 are transformed by parameter alpha in each.

910

911 **Figure 4.** Effects of increasing α on the ability of both phylogenetic and non-
912 phylogenetic predictors to inform distributions of species within simulated community
913 matrices. Boxplots are for species within community matrices ranked in quantiles from
914 those with less accurate models to more accurate ones, either modelled by phylogenetic
915 predictors (blue) or by non-phylogenetic random predictors (orange). Whereas model
916 accuracy increases, on average, with increasing α , there is large asymmetry in model
917 performance across species.

918

919 **Figure 5.** Model accuracy as measured by explained deviance in the distributions of
920 species within empirical examples modelled by either phylogenetic predictors (blue) or
921 non-phylogenetic random predictors (orange). Empirical datasets analysed comprise
922 Nearctic carnivores (A), Western Palaearctic mammals (B) and trees (C) and South
923 African Fabaceae (D). Note that both phylogenetic and non-phylogenetic predictors were
924 maximized by optimising α .

925

926 **Figure 6.** Variation in model accuracy comparing an environmental SDM including two
927 most frequently utilized environmental variables (i.e. mean annual temperature, Env.1,
928 and annual precipitation, Env.2) to an SDM including both environmental variables plus
929 the phylogenetic predictor. Models are for species belonging to five empirical examples
930 of Nearctic carnivores (n=29 species), Western Palaearctic mammals (n=126 species),
931 Western Palaearctic trees (n=47 species) and South Africa Fabaceae (n=116 species).
932 Accuracy metrics (left) are variation in the True Positive Rate (Δ TPR), variation in the
933 True Negative Rate (Δ TNR), variation in model error rate (Δ Error rate) and variation in
934 explained deviance (Δ D²). Variable importance, measured as mean decrease in accuracy
935 associated with the environmental (Env.1 and Env.2, green color) and phylogenetic
936 (Phylo predictor, blue color) predictors, is shown (right), indicating that the phylogenetic
937 predictor is usually as important as the second best environmental predictor (see
938 Appendix S2 in Supporting Information for details on modelling of case studies).
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941 Figure 1.

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945 Figure 3.

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951 Figure 5

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954 Figure 6